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Uranium anode

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Christian Häggström

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TORSHAMNSGATAN 30F | 164 40 KISTA | SWEDEN
+46 8 599 06 100 | INFO@OREXPLORE.COM | OREXPLORE.COM

Higher Z is more efficient

Kramers' law shows that the quantum efficiency of bremsstrahlung photon production scales linearly with the atomic weight of the anode target material (Kramers, 1923). The highest naturally occurring element is Uranium, but in this report also Thorium is evaluated.

Theoretical calculation

The source spectrum was calculated with Penelope 2008 Monte-carlo simulation package (Salvat, 2008). 10^5 electrons per target material were simulated and the resulting spectra is shown below. The electron energy is 120 keV.

Gold

To excite K lines of gold, photons need to be more energetic than 80.7 keV. As seen in the plot, Tungsten anode is exceptionally bad since its characteristic peak is below this limit. The 30% boost of electrons is partially because of higher Z and partially because the characteristic peak is on the correct side of gold's excitation energy.

Heat dissipation

In micro-focus x-ray sources the limiting factor of power is the heat generated on a small spot on the anode. It needs to be conducted away. Common practices are placing the anode on copper, or use a rotating anode to spread out the heat. How to deal with the bad heat conductance of Uranium and Thorium is beyond the scope of this document.

Summary

Element, atomic number	Relative yield (Kramers)	Relative gold excitation efficiency (Penelope)	Sublimation point at 10^{-8} Pa (Honig & Kramer)	Thermal conductivity
Tungsten, 74	100 %	100 %	2100 K	173 W/(m·K)
Thorium, 90	122 %	131 %	1500 K	54.0 W/(m·K)
Uranium, 92	124 %	136 %	1300 K	27.5 W/(m·K)

Sources

Kramers, H.A. (1923). "On the theory of X-ray absorption and of the continuous X-ray spectrum". *Phil. Mag.* **46**: 836. [doi:10.1080/14786442308565244](https://doi.org/10.1080/14786442308565244).

Salvat, Francesc. 2008. Penelope.

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